

	miR Name	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
A	has_miR_143_5p	NC_045512.2	23397	-19.90	ATCAG-GATGT-TAACTGCACA : TGGTCTCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	1.01E-1
B	has_miR_143_5p	OR134577.1	5919	-20.90	TGCAGTACGGCAGCTTCTGCACC TGGTCTCTACGTCG-TGACGTGG	1.64E-1
C	has_miR_143_5p	OK120841.1	2261	-20.90	TGCAGTACGGCAGCTTCTGCACC TGGTCTCTACGTCG-TGACGTGG	2.04E-1

Fig. 1. Representative RNA22 v2 prediction for high-affinity miR-143-5p binding sites on all three targets.

(A) SARS-CoV-2 genome (NC_045512.2; 23397nt - Spike Protein [SP] gene), (B) Pfizer BNT162b2 sequence (OR134577.1; 5919nt) and (C) Moderna mRNA-1273 sequence (OK120841.1; 2261nt). Data of entire analysis is available in [Supplementary Data - S1](#).